

ON THE COMPOSITION AND CONSTITUTION OF ETHYLENEBIGUANIDE

BY KSHITISRANJAN CHAKRAVARTY AND PRIVADARANJAN RÂY

While preparing ethylenebiguanide according to the method proposed by Dittler, and followed by Dübsky and co-workers, it was found that the product, obtained by us, differed from that of Dittler as revealed by its properties and composition. The analysis of the product showed that it was a dibiguanide and should be named ethylene-dibiguanide. This is further verified by the analysis of its copper derivatives.

In course of an investigation on metal-biguanide complexes, ethylenebiguanide sulphate was prepared in accordance with the method described by Dittler (*Monatsh*, 1908, 29, 647). The substance, on analysis, was found to differ in composition from that of Dittler and to possess somewhat different properties. Dübsky, Langer and Strand (*Collection*, 1938, 10, 111), who prepared the same substance following Dittler's method, assumed the composition given by the latter worker without making a complete analysis of the product. The results of analysis by different workers of their products are given below.

	Dittler (dried at 105°)	Dübsky and co-workers (dried at room temperature)	Chakravarty and Rây (thrice recrystallised and dried at room temp.)
C	... 21'54%	...	16'10, 15'85%
H	... 4'76	...	4'70, 5'31
N	... 31'25	33'76	30'40, 31'0
SO ₄	... 42'67	43'41	42'50, 42'50
			H ₂ O (by loss at 105°) ... 5'90%
			(SO ₄ for the anhydrous substance) ... 45'15, 45'20%

Calc. for (C₄H₉N₃), H₂S(O)₄: C, 21'33; H, 4'89; N, 31'11; SO₄, 42'73 %.

Calc. for (C₆H₁₆N₁₀)·2H₂SO₄·1'5H₂O: C, 15'96; H, 4'20; N, 31'04; SO₄, 42'57 (when anhydrous, 45'29); H₂O, 6'0%.

The method of preparation described by Dittler is given below.

One mol. of ethylenediamine hydrochloride (8 g.) and one mol. of dicyandiamide (5g.) finely divided condition were melted together with continuous stirring to a homogeneous viscous mass at a temperature of 140-50°. The process was stopped at the latter temperature, since decomposition set in at a few degrees higher. From the aqueous solution of the melt, the unused dicyandiamide was removed by repeated crystallisation. The filtrate, after some evaporation, was treated with a solution of copper sulphate. An immediate voluminous rose-red silky precipitate was obtained. For purification the precipitate was dissolved in dilute sulphuric acid till the red colour disappeared and reprecipitated with caustic soda. The product was washed with cold water. {Yield: 7 g. from 26 g. of the mixture (approx. 25%)}

The copper ethylenebiguanide compound was found by Dittler to be somewhat soluble in cold water and easily soluble in caustic liquor with a red colour (in viel kaltem Wasser etwas, in Natronlauge leicht mit roter Farbe gelöst werden könnte.). He recrystallised the copper compound from hot water for analysis.

For the preparation of ethylenebiguanide sulphate the above-described copper compound was dissolved in the least possible quantity of very dilute sulphuric acid; copper was removed by H₂S. The filtrate, on treatment with alcohol, gave a needle shaped crystalline precipitate, which was washed with alcohol. This was pure ethylenebiguanide sulphate, having the composition, (C₄H₉N₃)·H₂SO₄.

Dübsky and co-workers, who followed the same method, obtained, however, a very poor yield of the copper compound : only 3 g. from 50 g. of the mixture (50 g. mélange réactionnel ne donnent que 3 gr. de produit cuivrique).

The maximum yield obtained by us following this method, never exceeded 0.5 g. of the copper compound from 13 g. of the mixture containing the starting substances. We, however, succeeded in considerably improving the yield by the previous addition of a small quantity of copper sulphate (1 g.) to the reaction mixture (13 g.) and maintaining it with constant stirring at 140-45° for a sufficiently long time (1 hour) in order to obtain a perfectly homogeneous blue-coloured mass. On treatment with slightly ammoniacal water, the copper compound was left behind as rose-red, insoluble, silky residue. (Yield, 1.5 g. from 13 g. of the mixture). Further improvement in the yield was made by using mixtures in the proportion of 1 mol. ethylenediamine hydrochloride and 2 mol. of dicyandiamide. Mr. H. Sahu in this laboratory obtained an yield of about 9.5 g. of the copper compound by fusing a mixture of 20 g. ethylenediamine hydrochloride, 25 g. dicyandiamide and 8 g. copper sulphate. The copper compound as prepared by us, and presumably that of Dübsky and co-workers, was, unlike that of Dittler's product, very sparingly soluble in cold water, and we failed to recrystallise the product as Dittler had done.

For the preparation of ethylenebiguanide sulphate from its copper derivative we made a departure from Dittler's procedure. The copper compound was decomposed with moderately strong (1:1) sulphuric acid in the cold. On cooling the mixture, practically the whole of the ethylenebiguanide sulphate separated out in large rectangular prismatic crystals. These were recrystallised from a large quantity of hot water, containing a little sulphuric acid. Thus prepared, the substance was found to be difficultly soluble in cold water and perfectly stable in air: whereas Dittler describes his ethylenebiguanide sulphate as a hygroscopic, though not deliquescent, salt easily soluble in water, but insoluble in alcohol and ether. "Das Salz ist hygroscopisch, aber nicht zerfließlich, in Wasser leicht, in Alkohol und Aether nicht löslich."

Dittler's product therefore differs from ours and possibly also from that of Dübsky and co-workers, in its solubility and capacity for hydration, besides in composition already referred to.

The composition of the copper compound also differs in a similar manner. The following table gives the results of analysis of the copper derivative as found by different workers.

Dittler.	Dübsky & co-workers.	Chakravarty & Rây.
Cu : 13.44, 13.47 %	14.74, %	14.73, 14.71 %
Do (anhydrous) : 15.06, 15.10	...	16.43, 16.32
SO ₄ : 20.10, 20.40	22.70	22.32
Do (anhydrous) : 23.23, 23.58	...	24.77
N : ...	33.57	32.40
C : ...	...	17.10
H : ...	...	4.96
H ₂ O (by loss at 110°) : 11.90, 11.31 %	6.36%	12.20%

Calc. for (C₄H₈N₆)₂.Cu.H₂SO₄.3H₂O...(Dittler) :—

Cu, 13.60; SO₄, 20.53; N, 30.0; C, 20.53; H, 5.13; H₂O, 11.55%.

Calc. for (C₄H₈N₆)₂.Cu.H₂SO₄.H₂O...(Dübsky & co-workers) :—

Cu, 14.73; SO₄, 22.24; N, 32.44; C, 22.24; H, 4.63; H₂O, 4.17%.

Calc. for (C₆H₁₄N₁₀).Cu.H₂SO₄.2.5H₂O...(Chakravarty and Rây) :—

Cu, 14.70; SO₄, 22.19; N, 32.36; C, 16.64; H, 4.85; H₂O, 10.40%.

The anhydrous ($C_6H_{14}N_{10}$). $Cu.H_2SO_4$ requires Cu, 16'41 ; SO_4 , 24'77%.

An analysis of the corresponding complex copper chloride, also prepared by us, gave the following results : Cu, 16'46 ; Cl, 18'30 ; N, 36'10 ; C, 18'20, 18'76 ; H, 5'20, 5'31%. ($C_6H_{14}N_{10}$). $Cu.2HCl.1.5H_2O$ requires Cu, 16'32 ; Cl, 18'22 ; N, 35'93 ; C, 18'48 ; H, 4'88 per cent.

From a consideration of all the facts it may be concluded that the product, as obtained by us, differs from that of Dittler in composition. Regarding its constitution it may be represented as ethylene-dibiguanide as shown below ; and its mechanism of formation therefore follows that of simple biguanide :

Dittler represents the formation of his product, the ethylene monobiguanide, as follows, in which 1 mol. of ethylenediamine reacts with 1 mol. of dicyandiamide with liberation of 1 mol. of ammonia.

As ethylene monobiguanide, according to Dittler, forms a seven membered ring, which would lead to its instability, Dübsky and co-workers suggested a different constitution for this compound with a five-membered ring :

But we have failed to obtain ethylene monobiguanide even by closely following Dittler's method.

It is therefore concluded that the product, obtained by us, is ethylene-dibiguanide ; and its formation proceeds in the same way as that of *metaphenylenedibiguanide* (*cf.* Cohn, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1911, **84**, 394 ; Rây and Shidhanta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **20**, 200). It should therefore behave as a quadridentate molecule.

A large number of complex salts of ethylene-dibiguanide with metals like copper, nickel and cobalt have been described in a previous paper (Rây and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **20**, 291).

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